

A Study on Job Satisfaction of Scheduled Caste Teachers and their Attitude Towards Infrastructural Facilities and Curriculum at Primary Level

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ABSTRACT : The purpose of this study was to understand the scenario of scheduled caste primary teachers' job satisfaction and to understand the attitude of the scheduled caste primary teachers towards infrastructural facilities and curriculum. The study also tried to identify the relationship among job satisfaction and attitude towards infrastructural facilities and attitude towards curriculum. The total number of pupils in the sample was 103. Non parametric statistics were used to analyze data. Major findings of the study were that no significant relationship between job satisfaction of scheduled caste teachers and their attitude towards infrastructural facilities and attitude towards curriculum.

Keywords : Job satisfaction, Scheduled caste teachers, Attitude, Infrastructural facilities, Curriculum, Primary level.

Introduction

In teaching-learning process, a teacher is an essential component. If teacher does not get satisfaction on his job then the whole teaching-learning process cannot succeed smoothly. As there are no similar infrastructural facilities and curriculum in our country, it may effect their job satisfaction. The problem of the present research

is lying with the knowing of scheduled caste primary teachers' job satisfaction and attitude towards infrastructural facilities and curriculum in the district of Malda in West Bengal where there are total 15 blocks, among them 13 are educationally backward and 2 are non-educationally backward (pointed by Ministry of Human Resource, India).

Objectives of the study:

Present researchers will try to explore the following objectives:

- (i) To study and compare the job satisfaction of Scheduled caste primary teachers under different categorical variables like gender (M/F), strata (U/R), qualification (graduate/non graduate).
- (ii) To compare the attitude of the scheduled caste primary teachers towards infrastructural facilities of primary school under categorical variable.
- (iii) To compare the attitude of the scheduled caste primary teachers curriculum at primary level under categorical variable.
- (iv) To identify the relationship among job satisfaction and attitude towards infrastructural facilities and attitude towards curriculum.

Hypothesis of the study:

In the light of the above objective the following major hypotheses have been set up for the purpose of this investigation:-

H₀1. There would be no significant difference between the scheduled caste male teachers and the scheduled caste female teachers in their job satisfaction.

H₀2. There would be no significant difference between urban scheduled caste teachers and rural scheduled caste teachers in their job satisfaction.

H₀3. There would be no significant difference between scheduled caste graduate

teachers and scheduled caste non- graduate teachers in their job satisfaction.

H₀4. There would be no significant difference between scheduled caste male teachers and scheduled caste female teachers in their attitude towards infrastructural facilities.

H₀5. There would be no significant difference between urban scheduled caste teachers and rural scheduled caste teachers in their attitude towards infrastructural facilities.

H₀6. There would be no significant difference between scheduled caste graduate teachers and scheduled caste non- graduate teachers in their attitude towards infrastructural facilities.

H₀7. There would be no significant difference between scheduled caste male teachers and scheduled caste female teachers in their attitude towards curriculum.

H₀8. There would be no significant difference between urban scheduled caste teachers and rural scheduled caste teachers in their attitude towards curriculum.

H₀9. There would be no significant difference between scheduled caste graduate teachers and scheduled caste non- graduate teachers in their attitude towards curriculum.

H₀10. There would be no significant relationship between job satisfaction of scheduled caste teachers and their attitude towards infrastructural facilities and curriculum.

Methodology of the study:**Sample:**

The sample was selected randomly from the different Bengali medium [WBBPE] schools Gazole and Bamangola blocks of Malda district.

The teachers were from urban and rural areas. Number of sample is 103.

Variable in the present study:

The variables in the present study are:

Major variables: Job Satisfaction, Infrastructural Facilities, Curriculum.

Categorical Variables: Gender [Male & Female], Strata [Rural & Urban], Qualification [Graduate & Non-Graduate]

Tools for data collection:

For the collection of data, job satisfaction scale and attitude towards infrastructural facilities scale, attitude towards curriculum scale developed by researchers will be used. The scale was composed with 40 questions divided in Positive and Negative ratio with three dimensions. They are: 1. Job Satisfaction, 2. Attitude towards infrastructural Facilities, 3. Attitude towards Curriculum. Each item has five categories of responses which are: Strongly Agree, Agree, Do not know, Disagree and Strongly disagrees and 5-4-3-2-1 is the respective scores to be awarded for the responses. Scoring is done in reverse order for Negative items. There are 16 questions (1-16) about ‘Job Satisfaction’, 12 questions (17-28)

about ‘Infrastructural Facilities’, and 12 questions (28-40) about curriculum.

For the collection of data, three scales were developed by the present researchers, the scales were-

1. Job Satisfaction Scale for Primary School Teachers (JSSPST)
2. Attitude towards Infrastructural Facilities Scale (AIFS)
3. Attitude towards Primary Curriculum Scale (APCS)

Analysis and interpretation of data:

The data collected so by the investigators were analysed through various statistical techniques. Researchers used some statistical tests, there are- Spearman’s rho test, Mann-Whitney test, Wilcoxon W test etc. Spearman’s test used to analysis the data for finding the correlations between job satisfaction of schedule caste teachers and their attitude towards infrastructural facilities and attitude towards curriculum. Mann- Whitney test used to testing hypotheses of the study. The data collected was analyzed to test the hypotheses and conclusions were draw. All this are calculated through the help of SPSS.

Testing hypothesis:

Testing of H_0 1:

NPar Tests_ Gender (Mann-Whitney Test)

Table:1

Ranks

	GENDER	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
JOB SATISFACTION	MALE	72	50.43	3631.00
	FEMALE	31	55.65	1725.00
	Total	103		

Test Statistics

	JOB SATISFACTION
Mann-Whitney U	1003.000
Wilcoxon W	3631.000
Z	-.816
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.415

Interpretation:

For comparing the job satisfaction of male and female S.C teachers, the Mann – Whitney test was conducted and the calculated ‘U’ value found as 1003.00 and $Z = -0.816$. The ‘P’ value is 0.415 ($P > 0.05$) hence the null hypothesis is retained. It can be concluded that male and female S.C teachers do not differ significantly in their job satisfaction.

Testing of H_0 :**NPar Tests_ Gender (Mann-Whitney Test)****Table:2****Ranks**

	LOCATION OF SCHOOL	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
JOB SATISFACTION	RURAL	59	56.59	3339.00
	URBAN	44	45.84	2017.00
	Total	103		

Test Statistics

	JOB SATISFACTION
Mann-Whitney U	1027.000
Wilcoxon W	2017.000
Z	-1.814
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.070

Interpretation:

For comparing the job satisfaction of urban and rural teachers, the Mann – Whitney test was conducted and the calculated ‘U’ value found as 1027.00 and $Z = -1.814$. The ‘P’ value is 0.070 ($P > 0.05$) hence the null hypothesis is retained. It can be concluded that urban and rural teachers do not differ significantly in their job satisfaction.

Testing of H_03 :**NPar Tests_ Gender (Mann-Whitney Test)****Table:3****Ranks**

	QUALIFICATION	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
JOB SATISFACTION	NON-GRADUATE	54	49.80	2689.00
	GRADUATE	49	54.43	2667.00
	Total	103		

Test Statistics

	JOB SATISFACTION
Mann-Whitney U	1204.000
Wilcoxon W	2689.000
Z	-.789
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.430

Interpretation:

For comparing the job satisfaction of non-graduate and graduate S.C teachers, the Mann – Whitney test was conducted and the calculated ‘U’ value found as 1204.00 and $Z = -0.789$. The ‘P’ value is 0.430 ($P > 0.05$) hence the null hypothesis is retained. It can be concluded that graduate and non-graduate S.C teachers do not differ significantly in their job satisfaction.

Testing of H_04 :**NPar Tests_ Gender (Mann-Whitney Test)****Table:4****Ranks**

	GENDER	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
INFRASTRUCTURAL FACILITY	MALE	72	51.98	3742.50
	FEMALE	31	52.05	1613.50
	Total	103		

Test Statistics

	INFRASTRUCTURAL FACILITY
Mann-Whitney U	1114.500
Wilcoxon W	3742.500
Z	-.011
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.991

Interpretation:

For comparing the attitude towards infrastructural facilities of male and female S.C teachers at primary level , the Mann – Whitney test was conducted and the calculated ‘U’ value found as 1114.500 and $Z = -0.011$ The ‘P’ value is 0.991 ($P > 0.05$) hence the null hypothesis is retained. It can be concluded that male and female teachers do not differ significantly in their attitude towards infrastructural facilities.

Testing of H_0 :**NPar Tests_ Gender (Mann-Whitney Test)****Table:5****Ranks**

	LOCATION OF SCHOOL	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
INFRASTRUCTURAL FACILITY	RURAL	59	51.23	3022.50
	URBAN	44	53.03	2333.50
	Total	103		

Test Statistics

	INFRASTRUCTURAL FACILITY
Mann-Whitney U	1252.500
Wilcoxon W	3022.500
Z	-.304
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.761

Interpretation:

For comparing the attitude towards infrastructural facilities of urban and rural S.C primary teachers , the Mann – Whitney test was conducted and the calculated ‘U’ value found as 1252.500

and $Z = -0.304$ The 'P' value is $0.761 (P > 0.05)$ hence the null hypothesis is retained. It can be concluded that urban and rural teachers do not differ significantly in their attitude towards infrastructural facilities.

Testing of H_06 :

NPar Tests_ Gender (Mann-Whitney Test)

Table:6

Ranks

	QUALIFICATION	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
INFRASTRUCTURAL FACILITY	NON-GRADUATE	54	50.94	2750.50
	GRADUATE	49	53.17	2605.50
	Total	103		

Test Statistics

	INFRASTRUCTURAL FACILITY
Mann-Whitney U	1265.500
Wilcoxon W	2750.500
Z	-.380
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.704

Interpretation:

For comparing the attitude towards infrastructural facilities of graduate and non-graduate S.C primary teachers, the Mann – Whitney test was conducted and the calculated 'U' value found as 1265.00 and $Z = -0.380$ The 'P' value is $0.704 (P > 0.05)$ hence the null hypothesis is retained. It can be concluded that graduate and non-graduate S.C primary teachers do not differ significantly in their attitude towards infrastructural facilities.

Testing of H_07 :

NPar Tests_ Gender (Mann-Whitney Test)

Table:7

Ranks

	GENDER	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
ATTITUDE TOWARDS CURRICULUM	MALE	72	54.85	3949.50
	FEMALE	31	45.37	1406.50
	Total	103		

Test Statistics

	ATTITUDE TOWARDS CURRICULUM
Mann-Whitney U	910.500
Wilcoxon W	1406.500
Z	-1.481
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.139

Interpretation:

For comparing the attitude towards curriculum of male and female S.C primary teachers , the Mann – Whitney test was conducted and the calculated ‘U’ value found as 910.00 and $Z = -1.481$. The ‘P’ value is 0.139 ($P > 0.05$) hence the null hypothesis is retained. It can be concluded that male and female S.C primary teachers do not differ significantly in their attitude towards curriculum.

Testing of H_0 :**NPar Tests_ Gender (Mann-Whitney Test)****Table:8****Ranks**

	LOCATION OF SCHOOL	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
ATTITUDE TOWARDS CURRICULUM	RURAL	59	51.59	3044.00
	URBAN	44	52.55	2312.00
	Total	103		

Test Statistics

	ATTITUDE TOWARDS CURRICULUM
Mann-Whitney U	1274.000
Wilcoxon W	3044.000
Z	-.160
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.873

Interpretation:

For comparing the attitude towards curriculum of rural and urban S.C primary teachers , the Mann – Whitney test was conducted and the calculated ‘U’ value found as 1274.00 and $Z = -0.160$. The ‘P’ value is 0.873 ($P > 0.05$) hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It can be concluded that urban and rural S.C primary teachers do not differ significantly in their attitude towards curriculum.

Testing of H_0 :**NPar Tests_ Gender (Mann-Whitney Test)****Table:9****Ranks**

	QUALIFICATION	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
ATTITUDE TOWARDS CURRICULUM	NON-GRADUATE	54	48.38	2612.50
	GRADUATE	49	55.99	2743.50
	Total	103		

Test Statistics

	ATTITUDE TOWARDS CURRICULUM
Mann-Whitney U	1127.500
Wilcoxon W	2612.500
Z	-1.294
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.196

Interpretation:

For comparing the attitude towards curriculum of graduate and non-graduate S.C primary teachers , the Mann – Whitney test was conducted and the calculated ‘U’ value found as 1127.00 and $Z = -1.294$ The ‘P’ value is 0.196($P > 0.05$) hence the null hypothesis is retained. It can be concluded that graduate and non-graduate S.C primary teachers do not differ significantly in their attitude towards curriculum.

Testing of H_0 :**Nonparametric Correlations:****Table no:10**

			JOB SATISFACTION
Spearman's rho	JOB SATISFACTION	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.
		N	103
	INFRASTRUCTURAL FACILITY	Correlation Coefficient	.092
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.358
		N	103
	ATTITUDE TOWARDS CURRICULUM	Correlation Coefficient	.148
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.135
		N	103

Interpretation

To study the relationship between job satisfaction and attitude towards infrastructural facility, the non-parametric correlation statistic was calculated and the Spearman's rho was found to be 0.092 and P value was 0.358 ($P > 0.05$) hence null hypothesis is retained. Hence we can say that job satisfaction and attitude towards Infrastructural facility has no significant correlation.

To study the relationship between job satisfaction and attitude towards curriculum, the non-parametric correlation statistic was calculated and the Spearman's rho was found to be 0.148 and P value was 0.135 ($P > 0.05$) hence null hypothesis is retained. Hence we can say that job satisfaction and attitude towards Curriculum has no significant correlation.

Conclusion

In earlier days, a teacher was respectable to all. But this has been changed as the time progresses. But it is undeniable that the teacher is the main builder of society. The teacher is the main pillar of education system. A teacher success is mainly depended on how teachers are getting satisfaction from their job. Besides, the more Infrastructural facilities and Curriculum effective are, the more smooth and flexible will be teaching- learning process. The reason of the teacher's eligibility can create difference in teaching process. Though the teacher is eligible to teach at high school, he is compelled to teach at primary school. In this case, he may not get job satisfaction. In many cases, they are significant difference in job satisfaction among male and female teachers. But in most cases,

teachers think that they are not paid enough salary according to their labour. This is a major issue for not getting the job satisfaction. Some teachers think that the mid-day meal scheme create problem in teaching- learning process. Though most of the teachers do not agree with that. Most of the teachers think that the Infrastructural facilities are good; it is easy to conduct the teaching learning process. Though some the teachers think that infrastructural facilities are not a major factor to conduct the teaching learning process. Yet most of the teachers think that the teaching learning process will smooth and flexible if there is adequate arrangement of Infrastructural facilities such as the common room of the teachers, playing ground, number of teachers and proper teaching learning aids.

According to large number of S.C teachers the curriculum of Bengali and mathematics at primary level does not create problem as the curriculum of English does among the teachers to teach the students. The proper step should be taken to teach English. Most of the teacher thinks that there is possibility of correlation method in curriculum. A large number of teachers think that co-curricular activity should be more at primary level. The co-curricular activity should be included more in the curriculum at primary level. There is positive and negative opinion on whether this curriculum should be effective or not in the field of all round development of the children. The government should take much more care about this. If the teachers get more satisfaction from their jobs and attitude towards Infrastructural facilities and curriculum be positive, then teaching learning process will be much more effective.

At the primary level male & female S.C teachers, rural & urban S.C teachers and graduate & non - graduate S.C teachers do not differ significantly in their job satisfaction. So we may conclude that Categorical variables (gender, strata, qualification) do not make any significant difference in job satisfaction. Mean of job satisfaction is moderately high among them.

There is no significant difference of attitude towards Infrastructural Facilities among male & female S.C teachers, rural & urban S.C teachers and graduate & non graduate S.C teachers at primary level. From this study we may conclude that with the change of categorical variables (gender, strata, qualification) attitude towards Infrastructural Facilities is not changed. From the study, it is seen that mean of attitude towards Infrastructural Facilities is moderately high.

There is no significant difference of attitude towards Curriculum among male & female S.C teachers, rural & urban S.C teachers and graduate & non graduate S.C teachers at primary level. From this study we may conclude that with the change of categorical variables (gender, strata, qualification) attitude towards Curriculum is not changed. From the study, it is seen that mean of attitude towards Curriculum is moderately high.

From this study it is seen that job satisfaction and attitude towards Infrastructural Facilities or job satisfaction and attitude towards curriculum have no significant correlation. Job satisfaction of any teachers does not depend on Infrastructural Facilities and curriculum. So, Infrastructural Facilities and curriculum cannot

effect the job satisfaction of S.C primary teachers. At primary level S.C teachers are satisfied whether Infrastructural Facilities is good or bad. It is also same in the case of curriculum also. The positive or negative attitude of S.C primary teachers towards curriculum does not affect their job satisfaction. Never the less, we may say that job satisfaction of S.C primary teachers does not depend on Infrastructural Facilities or curriculum. It can depend on other variables also. From this study we may conclude that if a teacher has positive attitude of teaching, right ethics towards his profession, no variables easily effect their job satisfaction.

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